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Barriers and Breakthroughs: Education and Employment Opportunities of Transgenders in India

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ABSTRACT

Our nation celebrates its rich cultural diversity and is renowned for 'Unity in Diversity.' However, beneath this lies a troubling reality of gender inequality. While all genders are legally respected, societal attitudes towards transgender individuals remain prejudiced. Despite recognition, transgender people struggle for peace and harmony in our judgmental society. Globally, transgender individuals face profound social exclusion, limiting their access to education and employment, increasing health vulnerabilities, and curtailing opportunities for advancement. Societal hatred and aggression against those defying gender norms lead to extreme violence, perpetuating their marginalization and suffering. This paper examines the plight of transgender individuals, who remain primarily uneducated due to societal rejection and the lack of appropriate schooling. Even when they gain admission to educational institutions, they frequently endure harassment and bullying, leading to their expulsion or voluntary withdrawal from schools and colleges. The National Education Policy (N.E.P.) 2020 promises a more inclusive educational environment. Yet, deeply rooted cultural prejudices and systemic barriers must be addressed to eliminate long-standing inequities among transgender individuals. This paper explores the intricate interplay between policy intentions and practical implementations, offering insights into achieving true educational parity for transgender people in India.

Key Words: N.E.P., Education, Transgender, Barriers, Equality

INTRODUCTION

In our country, various socio-cultural groups of transgender people, including third gender, hijras, jogtas, eunuchs, jogappas, Kothis, Aravanis, sakhis, Shiv-Shaktis and aradhis, face severe discrimination and sexual harassment regularly. The word 'hijra' is a masculine noun... a less-than-perfect man. The term 'hijra' originates from the Persian word 'hiz,' signifying ineffectiveness and incompetence. Alternative appellations include hijada, hijara, and hijrah, often pronounced as 'heejda' or 'heejra'. Hijra denotes 'eunuchs' or the 'third gender'. 'Kinnar', an older term for hijras, is employed respectfully and formally. In Hindi, 'chhakka' serves as derogatory slang. In South India, hijras are named 'aravani' 'aruvani', or

'aravanni'. Male devotees dressing as females are called 'Jogappa'. 'Kothi' (or 'Koti') is commonly used

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throughout India. Urdu and Punjabi communities called them 'khusra' and 'Janka'. Gujarati people called them 'Pavaiyaa'. Local equivalents include 'Durrani' (Kolkata), 'Menaka' (Cochin), 'Meti' (Nepal), and 'zenana' (Pakistan). The concept of third gender or third sex denotes a gender category recognized in these societies, distinct from traditional male and female roles. These individuals are perceived as neither entirely male nor solely female, embodying linguistically, culturally, and legally distinct identities. In Indian culture, for instance, individuals born biologically male but identifying as female often become socialized as hijras.

HISTORICAL CONTEXT

Hijras, or transgender people, have been an integral aspect of Hindu society and culture, their existence dating back nearly 4,000 years, with references found in Vedic and Jain literature. Their historical importance is intricately interwoven into Hindu mythology and religious texts, which acknowledge a 'third sex' or individuals whose gender identity transcends the conventional male and female binaries. 'Tritiya Prakriti' or 'napunsaka' is central to Vedic and Puranic literature, where 'napunsaka' denotes the absence of procreative capability. In the Ramayana, when Lord Rama, exiled for 14 years, bids all "men and women" to return to the city, only the hijras remain, feeling unbound by his directive. Moved by their unwavering loyalty, Rama bestows upon them the power to bless individuals on auspicious occasions such as childbirth, marriage, and inaugural functions, thus establishing the tradition of badhai, wherein hijras sing, dance, and confer blessings.

In the Mahabharata, Aravan, the noble offspring of Arjuna and Nagakanya, offers himself as a sacrificial oblation to Goddess Kali, thus ensuring the Pandavas' triumph in the Kurukshetra war. His sole condition is to spend his last night in the wedding bonds. However, as no woman consents to wed a man fated for death, Krishna, in his divine compassion, transforms into Mohini, a resplendent maiden, and espouses him. In South India, hijras revere Aravan as their ancestral figure and affectionately refer to themselves as Aravanis.

In the heyday of the Mughal empire, transgender individuals held significant sway as administrators, political advisors, and carers of the harem, occupying esteemed roles within royal courts. Notable figures such as Itimad Khan eunuch officials in Akbar's court, managed state finances, accruing considerable wealth and influence. European visitors to Mughal India were

astounded by the opulent lifestyles and high status enjoyed by transgender individuals, recognizing their affluent and privileged positions.

Despite their long history, inequality for transgender communities emerged during British rule with the enactment of the Criminal Tribes Act in 1871, criminalizing these groups and drastically altering their social standing. Despite the repeal of this law in 1949, discrimination continues to endure. In contemporary usage, the umbrella term 'trans' encompasses both binary and nonbinary transgender individuals, as well as those who identify as genderqueer in diverse manners. Section 2(k) of The Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act, 2019 delineates a transgender person as one whose gender identity does not correspond with the gender assigned at birth. This definition encompasses trans men and trans women, irrespective of whether they have undergone sex removal surgery, laser therapy, hormone therapy, or any other form of medical intervention.

In a landmark decision on April 15, 2014, India's Supreme Court mandated the creation of a third gender category for transgender individuals, including Hijras. The court decreed that transgender people could now access educational institutions and employment opportunities under this designation, affirming their right to equal treatment without discrimination based on gender.

RELIGIOUS BELIEFS AND CULTURAL ACTIVITIES

Hijras commonly worship Bahuchara Mata, Lord Shiva, or both as deities. They symbolically marry Lord Vishnu or Krishna and mourn his demise the following day with ritual dances and bangles breaking. An annual beauty contest is also part of their traditions. The primary temple dedicated to Bahuchara Mata in Gujarat is a pilgrimage site for hijras, who consider her their patroness. In North India, Ardhanari is revered and holds special significance as a deity embodying gender ambiguity and patronage for hijras. Muslim hijras are viewed as manifestations of Allah's divine will. It is rumoured that hijras can bestow blessings or curses in religious ceremonies.

The study examines obstacles faced by transgender individuals, evaluates governmental measures and the current state of transgender education, and analyzes the National Education Policy 2020's efforts and challenges in ensuring equitable access for marginalized groups, with a focus on transgender people.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study undertakes a comprehensive review of existing literature and policy documents, drawing extensively from secondary data sources, including academic texts, governmental records, policy papers, and reports. Through systematic review and thematic analysis, recurring themes and patterns pertinent to the initiatives and challenges of N.E.P. 2020 in fostering transgender-inclusive education were identified. These insights were critically evaluated to assess the policy’s effectiveness and to pinpoint any deficiencies in its design and implementation concerning transgender education.

DISCUSSION

For numerous years, the Indian Census had hitherto failed to recognize the third gender, namely transgender individuals, within its demographic surveys. Nevertheless, the 2011 Census heralded a historic milestone by incorporating the enumeration of the ‘trans’ population nationwide. The statistics pertaining to their population and literacy rate in 2011 were as follows:

States and Literacy Rate among Transgenders

States	Transgender	
	Person	Literacy
Uttar Pradesh	137,465	55.80%
Andhra Pradesh	43,769	53.33%
Maharashtra	40,891	67.57%
Bihar	40,827	44.35%
West Bengal	30,349	58.83%
Madhya Pradesh	29,597	53.01%
Tamil Nadu	22,364	57.78%
Orissa	20,332	54.35%
Karnataka	20,266	58.82%
Rajasthan	16,517	48.34%
Jharkhand	13,463	47.58%
Gujarat	11,544	62.82%
Assam	11,374	53.69%
Punjab	10,243	59.75%
Haryana	8,422	62.11%

Chhatisgarh	6,591	51.35%
Uttarakhand	4,555	62.65%
Delhi	4,213	62.99%
Jammu Kashmir	4,137	49.29%
Kerela	3,902	84.61%
Himachal Pradesh	2,051	62.10%
Manipur	1,343	67.50%
Tripura	833	71.19%
Meghalaya	627	57.40%
Arunachal Pradesh	495	52.20%
Goa	398	73.90%
Nagaland	398	70.75%
Puducherry	252	60.59%
Mizoram	166	87.14%
Chandigarh	142	72.22%
Sikkim	126	65.18%
Daman and Diu	59	75.51%
Andaman & Nicobar Islands	47	73.81%
Dadra and Nagar Haveli	43	73.68%
Lakshadweep	2	50.00%
Total	487,803	56.07%

The above table indicates that the total transgender population in India in 2011 was 487,803, with state-wise distribution showing Uttar Pradesh had the largest number at 137,465 and Lakshadweep the smallest with only two transgender residents. The national literacy rate averages 74.04%, whereas it is 56.07% among transgender individuals, highlighting a significant disparity compared to binary genders. In Mizoram, transgender individuals have the highest literacy rate at 87.14%, while Bihar records the lowest at 44.14%.

In 2014, Shahla Tabassum and Sadia Jamil conducted a study in Rawalpindi, Pakistan, exploring the educational perspectives within the transgender community. The study found that 94% of respondents acknowledged the crucial role of education in personal growth and social advancement. They expressed a keen interest in education tailored to their specific needs. Conversely, 6% were unsure about education’s importance,

prioritizing immediate livelihood concerns. Among the participants, 72% believed that education could catalyze positive change in their lives, contrasting with 20% who felt uncertain, emphasizing societal attitudes as pivotal. An additional 8% expressed scepticism, citing entrenched social prejudice that renders education ineffectual. The study also revealed that 48% believed education could enhance job prospects, while 28% saw governmental interventions as crucial.

Education is pivotal for socio-economic advancement, nurturing individuals' and nations' physical, mental, and spiritual well-being. It is a potent instrument for social empowerment, providing avenues to escape economic scarcity and disparity. Effective government policies are needed to uplift marginalized communities through social schemes. Transgender individuals facing extreme vulnerability require better educational opportunities to enhance their circumstances. Due to stigma, many endure societal rejection, even within their homes and schools. Ensuring a safe and inclusive educational environment is essential. Transgender students frequently encounter verbal and physical abuse, resulting in diminished academic achievements and increased rates of leaving school. Discrimination predicated upon sexual orientation and gender identity exacerbates their educational journey, underscoring the pressing necessity for systemic reform to guarantee equality and safety within academic environments.

Transgender individuals often find themselves ostracized from familial and educational spheres, their rights undermined by societal stigma, discrimination, and deprivation. Transgender children, in particular, are rendered vulnerable within public institutions such as schools, where the attitudes of both educators and peers are often lamentable. The school environment, steeped in rigid heteronormativity, compels these youth to suppress their true selves, leading to exclusion. Adolescence, a pivotal period for understanding social and cultural gender norms, becomes especially fraught, with gender expression and behaviour strictly policed by peers, friends, educators, and family alike.

The Booker Prize Winner author Arundhati Roy, in her famous book 'The Ministry of Utmost Happiness', narrates the educational challenges that transgender face. She writes that at the age of five, Aftab, the protagonist of the novel, began his education at the Urdu-Hindi Madrassa for boys, where he quickly mastered a substantial portion of the Quran in Arabic within a single year. While showing above-average academic ability,

Aftab's true passion and innate talent blossomed in music, which is evident from a young age. Recognizing his potential, his parents enrolled him under the tutelage of Ustad Hameed Khan, a renowned musician. Despite initial encouragement, Aftab soon faced ridicule from other children, who mocked his gender identity. The relentless teasing became unbearable, leading Aftab to withdraw from regular school attendance. However, he continued his music education privately with the unwavering support of Ustad Hameed. Despite this refuge, the emotional scars inflicted by his peers persisted, casting a shadow over any prospect of reconciliation.

On April 15, 2014, the Apex Court of India rendered its landmark judgment in *National Legal Services Authority v. Union of India*, affirming the rights of transgender individuals across the nation. The court mandated the prohibition of discrimination and recommended formulating welfare policies, including reservations in educational institutions and employment opportunities. This judgment upheld the constitutional right of transgender persons to self-identify their gender without necessitating sex reassignment surgery. Since then, the transgender community in India has garnered significant and sustained attention from mainstream society. Then, the Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment released an Expert Committee Report after extensive consultations with transgender individuals. The Union Government of India enacted the Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act, 2019, which proscribes discrimination in the realms of education, employment, and healthcare services whilst also mandating provisions for the welfare of transgender individuals. Section 3(a) of the Act prohibits discriminatory practices in educational institutions. In contrast, Section 13 mandates inclusive education and equal sports, recreation, and leisure opportunities for transgender individuals in all government-recognized academic institutions.

The National Education Policy (N.E.P.) 2020 comprises various sections and initiatives to improve education for marginalized communities, though it does not explicitly address transgender education. While these provisions indirectly support expanding educational opportunities and inclusivity, they lack specific protections for transgender individuals. This highlights the necessity for bespoke policies specifically planned to accommodate to the distinct needs of transgender students in the broader context of marginalized communities.

Key excerpts from N.E.P. 2020 highlight inclusivity:

- Inclusive Education (Section 6.1): Emphasizes equitable access to quality education for students from diverse backgrounds, including gender identity and socio-economic status.
- Flexible Learning (Section 3.5): Expands educational pathways through Open Distance Learning, catering to socio-economically disadvantaged groups.
- GIF4 (Section 6.8): Supports equitable access for girls and transgender students, addressing specific barriers like sanitation facilities and community-based interventions.
- Curriculum Reforms (Section 11.1): Promotes multidisciplinary learning to reduce gender bias and enhance understanding of societal issues.
- Teacher Training (Section 6.14): This includes sensitization in teaching children with special needs and fostering inclusivity.

While N.E.P. 2020 strives for inclusivity, specific policies are needed to ensure equitable education for transgender individuals, recognizing their unique challenges and requirements. The N.E.P. lacks specific anti-bullying measures for transgender students, neglecting their urgent need for protection from bullying, harassment, and discrimination. This oversight undermines their psychological well-being, self-worth, and academic success, given the pervasive societal stigma and misunderstanding surrounding transgender issues.

Numerous transgender individuals endure the anguish of gender dysphoria, a deep-seated discord between the gender assigned to them at birth and their authentic gender identity, leading to considerable emotional turmoil. According to the National Human Rights Commission's pioneering study on transgender rights in India, their rights are extensively compromised. Meta-analytic data highlight higher rates of mental health issues among LGBT populations, including hijras, compared to heterosexuals. Additionally, studies underscore their heightened vulnerability to alcohol and substance abuse disorders.

Concerning the economic opportunities of transgender people, a meticulous inquiry conducted by Pothole Raja (2020) reveals a bleak and discouraging panorama:

- 96% of transgender individuals face job denial, resorting to low-paying and undignified work like begging and sex work for survival.
- 89% report a lack of suitable job opportunities despite qualifications.
- 50-60% have never attended school, enduring severe discrimination when they did. The NHRC reports 52% harassment by classmates and 15% by teachers, leading many to abandon education.
- Only 6% are employed in private sectors or N.G.O.s.
- Only 1% of transgender individuals earn a monthly income exceeding Rs. 25,000, while the majority, 26.35%, have earnings between Rs. 10,000 and Rs. 15,000.
- A distressing 23% are driven to partake in perilous sex work, which drastically heightens their susceptibility to H.I.V., with transgender persons being 49 times more likely to contract the virus compared to the general populace.

CONCLUSION

Transgender individuals have inherent rights to life, liberty, equality, health, privacy, speech, and expression. Despite the Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act 2019 and the N.E.P. 2020, they still face educational challenges, including harassment from peers and educators. This hostile environment often leads to dropout rates. Achieving real change requires genuine acceptance through comprehensive education. Denying their identity and rights undermines the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development's goals. Transgender children, often abandoned due to societal pressures, endure stigma, instability, and financial insecurity. Establishing safe, educational environments and dedicated transgender schools with supportive staff is critical. Additionally, involving transgender advocates and counsellors in schools is essential, mirroring efforts for disabled individuals to ensure equitable education opportunities.

Undeniably, the realms of education and employment are intimately interwoven. The degree of one's education profoundly influences one's vocational prospects, and conversely, the nature of one's employment can impact one's educational pursuits. Generally, advanced education paves the way for superior job opportunities

and elevated wages, whereas the absence of education often results in underemployment or unemployment. The connection between education and employment is both intricate and multifaceted. Therefore, enhancing the educational standards for transgender individuals will concurrently elevate their economic prospects and employment opportunities. Some particular types of services for the transgender person should be identified, and provisions should be made for reservations and priorities in their appointments.

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Competing interests

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